

ASSESSING COMMON CAUSES OF DYSPHAGIA ON BARIUM SWALLOW AT REHMAN MEDICAL INSTITUTE (RMI), NORTHWEST GENERAL HOSPITAL (NWGH) AND LADY READING HOSPITAL (LRH) PESHAWAR

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Dysphagia, or difficulty swallowing, is a significant health concern that can lead to malnutrition and decreased quality of life. This research seeks to determine the root factors contributing to dysphagia across different age groups, emphasizing the importance of effective diagnostic tools like the barium swallow test in guiding appropriate management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Dysphagia, characterized by difficulties in swallowing, is a common condition (1). Dysphagia, a swallowing condition, is defined by the dysfunction of one or more components of the swallowing system (2). It is a prevalent condition that impacts individuals of all ages (3). According to recent research, older persons are more prone to develop dysphagia due to changes in the swallowing process that occur with age (4). Dysphagia for both solids and liquids can be caused by esophageal motility issues; however, dysphagia that initially affects solids and subsequently progresses to liquids is more commonly attributable to physical blockage (5). Structural abnormalities, whether non-cancerous or malignant, esophageal movement problems,

neuromuscular disorders, carcinomas, achalasia, esophagitis, strictures, medical procedures, and gastro-esophageal reflux disease can all induce dysphagia (6) (7). Up to one third of individuals reporting lower gastrointestinal symptoms may really have dysphagia resulting from esophageal reflux disease (8). Failure to promptly identify and address dysphagia may lead to severe problems, including aspiration, pneumonia, starvation, weight loss, and even death (9). Dysphagia may be categorized into three primary types: oral, pharyngeal, and esophageal, with oral and pharyngeal collectively referred to as oropharyngeal (10).

Epidemiology

Approximately 8% of the global population has dysphagia (11). Every year in the United States, 300,000 to 600,000 people suffer with dysphagia (12). A research conducted in Sydney found that 16% of people experience dysphagia at some point in their lives, with reflux being the most common cause (31.6%), strictures and Schatzki grey ring (4.8%), and eosinophilic esophagitis (1.8%)(13). According to available data, 11.4% of older adults in the United Kingdom and 33.7% in Korea have dysphagia symptom (14). In Pakistan, however, dysphagia affects 17% of the population between the ages of 44 and 49, and 23.3% of the population over 55. It is widely seen in intensive care units, with a recorded prevalence of 47.4%. It is prevalent across several illnesses, affecting 65% of people with acute stroke, 50% with Parkinson's disease, 31% with multiple sclerosis, 30% to 100% with motor neuron disease, and 13% to 57% with dementia (11).

Anatomy and physiology:

The esophagus is a muscular tubular structure commencing from the endodermal primitive gut, measuring 25 to 28 centimeters in length and around 2 centimeters in diameter (15). It starts as a continuation of the pharynx at the inferior boundary of the cricopharyngeal muscle located at the sixth cervical vertebra (16). The esophagus has three anatomical portions, extending from the sixth cervical vertebra to the eleventh thoracic vertebrae (17). The esophagus possesses a mostly cylindrical morphology with a fluctuating luminal diameter. The esophagus has three main functional areas: the upper esophageal sphincter, esophageal body, and the lower esophageal sphincter (18). The main purpose of the esophagus is to convey ingested food and liquids to the stomach while also preventing or eliminating gastroesophageal reflux (19). This function is executed systematically by the active contraction of both circular and longitudinal esophageal muscles (20). The swallowing mechanism comprises of the mouth, lips, the tongue, oral cavity, pharynx, airway, esophagus, and upper and lower sphincters (2).

Oral phase; The food is chewed in the mouth, creating a bolus, which is then propelled to the throat.

Pharyngeal phase; To swallow, the nasopharynx must be closed with the soft palate, while the larynx is lifted and closed with the epiglottis and thyroid cartilage.

Esophageal Stage; The food bolus enters into the esophagus and progresses to the stomach through peristalsis and the lower esophageal sphincter (21).

Types:

Dysphagia is thus the feeling of an obstruction to the usual flow of swallowed substances. It is a particular symptom that may arise intermittently in certain patients. It is additionally classified into two categories (22).

Oropharyngeal dysphagia:

The difficulty in starting the swallowing process is called oropharyngeal dysphagia (23). There is a challenge at the cervical vertebra to move food from mouth and pharynx to esophagus (21). Oropharyngeal dysphagia affects three major risk groups: older persons, people with neurological or neurodegenerative problems, and people with head and neck conditions (24). It is a physiological impairment in swallowing that disrupts airway safeguarding and the movement of bolus via the upper digestive system. The modified barium swallow test, also referred as video fluoroscopy, is the benchmark for assessing oropharyngeal dysphagia (25).

Esophageal dysphagia:

The sensation of struggling to move food or liquids from mouth to stomach is called esophageal dysphagia (4). Esophageal dysphagia is often attributed to primary and secondary esophageal movement abnormalities that impact either the whole neurological system or the mucosal layers of the esophagus (24). It is a typical symptom of a variety of gastrointestinal illnesses such as benign esophageal strictures, malignant esophageal strictures, esophagitis, esophageal foreign bodies, a fibrous ring within the esophagus, esophageal motility dysfunction, achalasia, esophageal spasm, and esophageal extrinsic compression (26). Esophageal dysphagia

should be delineated by assessing the nature of the foods that induce swallowing difficulties— whether solid, liquid, or both—along with the frequency of symptoms, their severity, and related manifestations such as weight loss, heartburn, or regurgitation (23). Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) is recommended as the primary diagnostic procedure for individuals suspected of esophageal dysphagia, succeeded by barium swallow if the results of EGD are negative (27).

Symptoms

Dysphagia is a sign of an underlying disease of damage, but it causes a variety of annoyances and problems. Among the main symptoms connected with dysphagia, we may discover

1. Discomfort and pain during swallowing
2. Food being expelled from the mouth
3. Excessive salivations
4. Difficulties closing the mouth entirely
5. Stuck sensations in the throat
6. Choked and watery voice
7. Repeated pneumonia (21).

Causes

Benign or malignant structural lesions, anomalies in esophageal motility, neuromuscular problems, neurological diseases (stroke, multiple sclerosis, Parkinson disease), carcinomas, achalasia, esophagitis, strictures, medical interventions and gastro-esophageal reflux syndrome can all cause dysphagia (6)(28)(21).

Achalasia:

Esophageal achalasia is a motility disorder of the esophagus marked by the inability of the lower esophageal sphincter to relax. The etiology is unknown. It is an uncommon in children, but if not addressed, it can cause serious health problems. Esophageal achalasia is an uncommon motor condition of the esophagus that results in the degeneration or loss of ganglion cells in the lower esophageal muscles layer (29). In addition, the lower smooth muscles exhibit aperistalsis (Fig 1). Clinical symptoms are used to diagnose achalasia, which is subsequently verified via esophagogastro- duodenoscopy, barium swallow, and manometry (30).

Figure 1: Achalasia (31)

Parkinson disease

It is a neurodegenerative illness characterized by gradual degradation of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia Nigra of the midbrain as well as multiple system involvement.

Dysphagia is a prevalent non-motor symptom in Parkinson’s patients, and it can lead to a variety of significant problems, including starvation and aspiration pneumonia. The incidence of dysphagia in Parkinson’s disease significantly differs among

countries, with reported rates of 32.0% in Israel and 87.1% in china (32).

Esophageal Cancer

Over fifty percent of patients with esophageal cancer presented with locally progressed distant metastases and tumor-associated symptoms

affecting their overall condition. The patient often exhibits cancer-related symptoms, including dysphagia, which deteriorates with disease progression, leading to discomfort, inadequate nutrition, diminished functioning, and a worse quality of life (fig 2) (33).

Figure 2: Advanced esophageal cancer in Barrett's esophagus (34)

Eosinophilic esophagitis:

From its first account in 1993, Eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) is recognized as a persistent inflammatory disorder, predominantly impacting younger males who experience persistent dysphagia, repeated food blockages, and possess a record of allergic conditions, eosinophilia or asthma (35). Eosinophilic esophagitis appears to

be caused by an allergy or is idiopathic, similar to eosinophilic gastroenteritis, which affects other sections of the gastrointestinal system (Fig 3). To accurately diagnose eosinophilic esophagitis, samples from the middle thoracic and distal esophagus, regardless of whether the mucosa seems normal, ought to be ordered for all patients experiencing unexplained dysphagia (27).

Figure 3: Eosinophilic esophagitis (35)

Reflux esophagitis:

In the beginning of 1980s, the advent of dual-contrast esophagography significantly enhanced the radiographic sensitivity for identifying reflux esophagitis, reportedly achieving 90% accuracy (36). The capacity to identify superficial ulcers and additional indicators of mild esophagitis, which were not apparent in single-contrast tests, were a notable benefit of the double-contrast approach (Fig 1.4). Early reflux esophagitis is often seen on dual-contrast scans as granulation in the lower esophagus, along with mucosal swelling and

inflammation (see Fig 4). Superficial ulcers manifest as punctate, linear, or serpiginous barium deposits, potentially accompanied by branching folds and the wrinkling or flattening of neighboring walls (36). In reflux esophagitis, ulcer formation often spreads upward from the gastroesophageal junction as a contiguous region of illness; hence, the existence of ulcers limited to the upper or middle esophagus should indicate an alternative etiology for the patient's condition (35).

Figure 4: Reflux esophagitis (35)

Obstructive lesion

Esophageal cancer, strictures, Schatzki rings, and webs should be assessed in individuals displaying

dysphagia. The incidence of these disorders is rather minimal, especially in those under fifty years of age (27).

Gastro Esophageal reflux

Gastro-esophageal reflux disease (GERD) is the prevalent esophageal condition in babies and children. It induces sporadic regurgitation or emesis. Even though it is a natural phenomenon in majority adults and children, it becomes pathogenic when its severity and occurrence escalates (31). In this scenario, prompt identification and intervention are essential to prevent potentially hazardous complications like

severe esophagitis, esophageal narrowing, and aspiration pneumonia. The upper gastrointestinal barium swallow (BS) series has long been the favored technique for imaging suspected esophageal reflux disease GERD (Fig 5). This sickness is commonly identified by clinical symptoms and endoscopic findings of esophageal mucosal damage. Heartburn and odynophagia are prevalent manifestations of GERD and correlate with the severity of endoscopic esophagitis (37).

Figure 5: Barium research. Reflux grading a) mild b) moderate c) severe (31)

Stroke

Stroke is categorized into two primary categories: ischemic and hemorrhagic, it is divided into three stages: the acute stroke stage, which lasts from the time the stroke occurs to two weeks; the sub-acute stage, which lasts from more than two weeks to six months; and the chronic stage, persisting beyond six months (38). A prevalent cause of dysphagia is brain injury resulting from a stroke. Each year, stroke ranks as the third foremost cause of mortality in the USA. The relationship between the site and extent of the stroke and subsequent dysphagia are complex; generally, a larger area of infarction correlates with more swallowing difficulties. Elevated stroke rates have been seen in older individuals and females, and these traits may correlate with an increased incidence of post-stroke dysphagia. In general, dysphagia is more common and severe in brain stem strokes than cortical strokes. Patients with right hemisphere strokes had increased pharyngeal dysfunction, such as aspiration and pharyngeal pooling (39). Various assessment strategies have been tried to

screen for post-stroke dysphagia in acute stroke, but no standard diagnostic tool has been agreed upon (38).

Multiple sclerosis

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmunity condition characterized by the immune system's assault on the central nervous system, particularly targeting myelin and oligodendrocyte cells. The immune system elicits a response that culminates in the development of sclerotic areas observable in various regions of central nervous system (CNS). It is the foremost catastrophic neurological disorder affecting young persons. The advancement of multiple sclerosis can lead to various sensory and motor impairments in the oral and facial area, potentially arising from nerve demyelination in the head and neck. The predominant clinical symptoms in the head and neck area encompass cranial glial cells, facial palsy, jaw joint abnormalities, vision related difficulties, dysphagia, and speech disorders. Cranial neuralgias encompass trigeminal neuralgia (TN),

glossopharyngeal neuralgia (GN), and occipital neuralgia (ON), which are indicative of neurological pain in multiple sclerosis (MS). These conditions are marked by episodic, excruciating sensations resembling electric shocks, which may occur spontaneously or be elicited by harmless stimuli in designated trigger zones (40).

Esophageal stricture:

Esophageal strictures are a prevalent concern in gastroenterology, and they may result from either malignant or benign lesions. This symptom affects every individual, irrespective of whether their strictures are produced by neoplastic or benign lesions (41). Patients suffering from progressive or solid meal dysphagia should be checked for esophageal strictures. Barium esophagograms and endoscopies can determine whether strictures are benign or cancerous. The bulk of benign strictures are acidic. If a peptic stricture is detected, esophageal dilatation with acid suppression drugs is the best treatment choice. Stent implantation is the most common intervention utilized to palliate malignant tissues. If dysphagia reoccurs, the dilation should be repeated. Refractory strictures can be treated with a range of procedures,

including corticosteroid injections, temporary implantation of selfexpandable plastic devices, and surgery (42).

Diffuse esophageal spasm:

Diffuse esophageal spasm (DES) is an unusual esophageal movement condition identified on barium scans by periodic lack of primary peristalsis with several profound (i.e., lumen blocking) non-propulsive contractions (NPCs), presenting a typical corkscrew (43). Prabhakar et al conducted a study in 2004, however, it was observed that individuals with DES commonly have minor to moderate NPCs (i.e., Not blocking the lumen). Approximately sixty-six percent of these individuals also show beak-like constriction of the lower esophagus due to poor opening of the LES (Fig 6) (44). Consequently, some experts feel that there is a relationship between DES and LES dysfunction, and that DES and achalasia exhibit opposing extremities of a spectrum of connected esophageal movement disorders, with a progressive progression from DES to achalasia occasionally happening with the passage of time (45).

Figure 6: Diffuse esophageal spasm with lower esophageal sphincter failure (44)

Barret's esophagus:

During the 1960s and 1970s, a mid-esophageal stricture was identified as a significant indicator of Barrett's esophagus in individuals with hiatal herniation and gastro- esophageal reflux (GER)

(Fig 7) (35). In 1983, a characteristic reticular pattern of the mucosa was identified as a highly distinctive indicator of Barrett's esophagus, especially when next to the distal portion of a severe stricture (46). A prominent Z line at the

raised squamous-columnar mucosal interface in individuals exhibiting substantial columnar

metaplasia is a recently identified characteristic of Barrett's esophagus (Fig 8) (34).

Figure 7: Barrett's esophagus with a high stricture (47)

Figure 8: Barrett's esophagus with a raised Z-line (34)

Peptic stricture:

Reflux esophagitis can cause circumferential scarring and peptic strictures in the lower esophagus, typically above a hiatal hernia (48). In the beginning of the 1980s, Ott et al established that a biphasic examination enhanced the precision of barium studies for identifying strictures; due to insufficient expansion of the lower esophagus in the upright position, single-contrast views were useful in identifying strictures

that were masked in upright double-contrast views (Fig 9) (49). Dilation with overlap between the lower esophagus and a neighboring hiatal hernia, which hinders visibility of the constricted segment in view (Fig 10a) (47). Peptic strictures generally present as smooth, tapering region of constriction (Fig. 1.10b) or, less commonly, as short, ring-shaped strictures in the lower esophagus (see Fig 11) (48).

Figure 9: Ring-shaped peptic stricture on prone single contrast view (48)

Figure 10: Ring-like peptic stricture on upright dual-contrast view (35)

Figure 11: Peptic stricture. Upright double-contrast view (49)

Complications:

Dysphagia has been demonstrated to dramatically damage the standard of living in affected persons with patients experiencing panic, anxiety and developing despair (50). It is a common clinical problem among older persons (51). The complication of dysphagia includes aspiration pneumonia, malnutrition, dehydration and weight loss (52).

Aspiration

Aspiration or inhaling foreign particles into the lower airway has historically been a substantial source of illness and death. Aspiration might be a single episode or a persistent condition. It can happen while eating or after eating during an episode of gastro-esophageal reflux disease. Abnormal or incorrect swallowing of drinks, food, or even saliva can contribute to aspiration in children (53).

Aspiration pneumonia

Dysphagia is typically connected with a variety of neurological conditions. If food beverages or oral secretions escape into the lungs due to oropharyngeal dysphagia, it can cause aspiration pneumonia. Aspiration pneumonia is potentially lethal. Adults are particularly vulnerable (54). Aspiration pneumonia has a high financial burden. It results in significant costs associated to lengthier hospitalization, mechanical breathing, and poor nutritional condition (55). Because aspiration pneumonia is caused by poor swallowing and cough reflexes, effective preventive interventions must incorporate the degradation of pharyngeal swallowing function, which is frequent in older adults (30).

Malnutrition.

Malnutrition is a medical condition defined by a disproportion of calories, proteins, and other nutrients, leading to noticeable adverse impacts on body composition, physical abilities, and health outcomes (51). Dysphagia can also be significant if the individual can not take enough food to sustain a healthy weight. Malnutrition may emerge if the disease is not appropriately detected, and it can weaken the immune system, making the patient

prone to infection. Additionally, people with dysphagia may have dehydration. Dysphagia, at the very least, is likely to diminish quality of life (54). Dysphagia appears to be linked to malnutrition (56).

Weight loss

Eating food and drinks is incredibly vital for our survival, mostly because it is the only natural means we have to receive the nutrients that our body requires. When we eat, the mouth, esophagus, larynx, and other components of the upper digestive system are involved. If there is any damage or problem with these parts, we will have difficulty swallowing (21). Weight change is widespread among persons with an average weight decrease of 4%. Dysphagia is actually connected with weight reduction in patients (57). Swallowing disorder dysphagia impacts the eating patterns of patients by making some foods difficult to eat, causing patients to eat less due to discomfort and experiencing weight loss (56).

Investigations

A comprehensive history is important for the examination of patients with dysphagia (58). For more than 40 years, evidence indicates that a thorough history can confirm the diagnosis in as many as 80% of individuals experiencing dysphagia. Patient history and demographics can significantly predict specific disorders, including carcinoma, peptic stricture, pharyngeal diverticulum, and eosinophilic esophagitis (59). The diagnosis starts with the physician obtaining and evaluating a comprehensive medical history, identifying the patient's symptoms (ROS), and doing a clinical assessment with any relevant diagnostic tests. Recent surgical or intubation records, recent diagnostic assessments, documented alterations in voice, instances of food regurgitation, any recorded history of coughing, or reports of food blockage in the throat are all components of the medical history and review of systems (ROS) (60). Dysphagia, as an alarm symptom, needs to be addressed urgently to determine the diagnosis early in the patient's therapy and exclude any persisting significant pathology, like tumor activity (60). There are three

areas of research in dysphagia: (a) endoscopy (b) manometry (c) barium swallow (3).

Barium swallow

The barium swallow, or esophagogram, is a recognized and often utilized diagnostic procedure for the esophagus. It provides details regarding both the structure and function of the esophagus (Fig 13, Fig 15). More precisely, the purpose is to evaluate anatomical anomalies, functional anatomy, esophageal contractility, peristalsis, and emptying (61). The barium study has developed into an accessible, noninvasive, and economical method that has the capability to streamline the selection of supplementary diagnostic procedures and inform selection for medical, endoscopic, or surgical treatment (35). Video fluoroscopy is regarded as the benchmark for evaluating the therapy for dysphagia (62). It consists of realtime video fluoroscopic recordings made as the patient swallow a range of boluses of varied consistencies and volumes, which permits the imaging of bolus passage through the upper gastrointestinal system in real time (Fig 12, Fig 14) (2). The examination is optimally conducted by a speech-language pathologist (SLP) and a radiologist, with the assistance of a radiologic technician, to concurrently assess anatomy and swallowing function in live observation (63). The data gathered during the assessment is crucial for recognizing and distinguishing the kind and degree of physiological swallowing impairment, assessing the safety of oral consumption, and formulating recommendations and treatment strategies for oral intake (25). The optimal approach for visualizing clinically suspected GERD is an upper GI series of barium swallow (64). It plays a critical function in detecting structural irregularities (e.g. Hiatus hernia, malrotation) (fig1) (31). The double-contrast approach has made the barium studies a valuable diagnostic procedure for reflux esophagitis, peptic strictures, and Barrett's esophagus. Early reflux

esophagitis is often defined on dual-contrast scans as granulation of the lower esophagus due to mucosal swelling and inflammation. The ulcer formation in reflux esophagitis nearly invariably reaches upward from the gastroesophageal junction as an uninterrupted region of illness [fig 2]. Performing a biphasic examination improved the correctness of barium studies in identifying strictures. Peptic stricture generally looks as smooth, tapering zones of constriction [fig 5] or, infrequently, as short ring-shaped strictures in the lower esophagus (see Figs. 3,4) (35). Barrett's esophagus can also be diagnosed via a modified barium swallow. Barrett's esophagus is characterized by an elevated Z line at the site of a raised squamo columnar mucosal interface in individuals with significant columnar metaplasia [Fig 8, Barrett's esophagus with raised z line](35). Eosinophilic esophagitis has been detected with markedly increased frequency by barium tests and endoscopy over the last twenty years, either attributable to a rising disease prevalence, heightened awareness, or a combination of both factors. In 2005, Zimmerman et al. documented significant ring-shaped impressions, resulting in a "ringed" esophagus which is nearly diagnostic for eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) in the appropriate medical situation. White et al identified a "narrow-diameter" esophagus as a further distinctive observation of EoE on barium tests [fig 1.7](35). Esophageal carcinoma can be identified more accurately with a dual contrast examination. On barium swallow, adenocarcinoma in the Distal esophagus. Appears as a non-uniform circular lesion with sharp, shelf-like upper and lower edges (arrows) [fig 8]. Barium esophagography has long been used to measure esophageal motility. Achalasia is a well-known esophageal motility condition identified on barium studies by absence of primary peristalsis on all swallows and tapering, beak-shaped constriction of the lower esophagus attributable to inadequate relaxation of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) [fig 9] (35).

Fig 12: Double contrast images of pharynx (65)

Fig 13: Normal double contrast image of esophagus (65)

Fig 14: Normal gastric cardia (65)

Fig 15: normal single contrast view of esophagus (65)

Endoscopy

Endoscopy is advised for patients with dysphagia to evaluate the underlying etiology, eliminate cancer and malignant diseases, assess the need for therapy, and undertake therapy such as dilation. Esophageal dilation is a therapeutic treatment performed to treat dysphagia. Endoscopy continues to be one of the finest initial investigations for accessing dysphagia and diagnosing premalignant and malignant conditions (66). Endoscopy not solely detects malignant and benign esophageal strictures but additionally diagnoses various anatomical abnormalities and mucosal disorders that are not readily identifiable using radiography methods, such as esophagitis. Nonetheless, it is recognized that the sensitivity of endoscopy for detecting minor benign strictures is insufficient. This is particularly applicable in eosinophilic esophagitis (61). It allows for direct viewing of the whole esophagus as well as the collection of tissue for biopsy. Infection, perforation, and cardio-pulmonary issues are the most common consequences. Upper GI endoscopy is a secure operation, with a complication rate of roughly 1% per 1000 operations (67).

Manometry

Esophageal manometry is a specialized examination that assesses the pressure of the lower and upper esophageal sphincters, along with the contraction, amplitude and peristaltic sequence of the esophageal body. The technique is clinically advantageous for evaluating individuals with nonstructural dysphagia (68). Although there are numerous techniques to assess esophageal motility dysfunction, manometry is the gold standard. Manometry has evolved from a research application to a clinically helpful and potentially widespread routine assessment for individuals with presumed esophageal movement dysfunction (69). In 1970, manometry emerged as an effective instrument for evaluating esophageal function. HRM enables professionals to assess both normal and pathological swallowing functions. The principal rationale for esophageal manometry is the assessment of dysphagia in the absence of conditions such as esophagitis, eosinophilic esophagitis, esophageal ulcers or strictures, and esophageal cancers. Esophageal manometry remains the most effective procedure for determining the upper boundary of the lower esophageal sphincter to ensure accurate pH probe placement (70). Manometry is the best method for

detecting primary esophageal movement disorders such as achalasia or diffuse esophageal spasm. Manometry may identify irregularities in the lower esophageal sphincter and esophageal body, which facilitate the advancement of pathological GERD (71).

Treatment:

Dysphagia is a symptom, and there are no particular curative therapies for it; instead, treatment focusses on addressing the underlying cause. Treatment for dysphagia is often palliative, aimed at enhancing the patient's swallowing ability or circumventing it, contingent upon the specific issue at hand. Dysphagia linked to neurological or systemic disorders is anticipated to deteriorate, necessitating surgical treatments such as gastrostomy for patient nourishment. If the reason is an infection, inflammation, or a tumor, the therapy will concentrate on eradicating these issues by pharmacological and surgical methods. If the issue arises from neurological alterations, medical irritations, or traumatic lesions, it is often addressed with medications such as pregabalin, lacosamide, or topiramate (21). Individuals exhibiting GERD symptoms, esophagitis, or peptic stricture should get acid suppression treatment utilizing a typical dosage of proton pump inhibitors for a duration of 8 to 12 weeks. Individuals with eosinophilic esophagitis may react to this treatment, however the majority need elimination diets, topical steroids, or a combination of both. For individuals experiencing functional dysphagia during full meals, avoiding trigger foods and trying acid suppression may be effective (27).

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

Descriptive Cross Sectional Study

Study Settings

This study was conducted at Rehman Medical Institute (RMI), Northwest General Hospital (NWGH) and Lady Reading Hospital (LRH).

Study Duration

from June 2024 to December 2024

Sample Size

Sample size was calculated by standard formula: $n = \frac{x^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2}$

Population proportion (P)=0.071 (88)

Level of confidence (x) = 95%

Margin of error (d) = 5% n=101

Sampling Technique

Non-probability Convenience sampling technique

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients experiencing signs of dysphagia referred for barium swallow investigation.
- Participants aged 1 to 80 years.
- Participants of any gender.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete records.
- Individuals below 1 year of age.
- People who may be allergic to contrast media.
- Pregnant women.
- Individuals aged above 80 years.

Data Collection Procedure

A retrospective observational methodology was used, with a focus on patient reports from people who had barium swallow tests. Data were carefully retrieved from medical records, capturing demographics, clinical findings, and recognized causes of dysphagia. demographics.

Data Analysis Procedure:

After collection, the data were imported into SPSS version 20 for analysis, where cleaning and verification were performed to ensure accuracy. Descriptive statistics, such frequencies and percentages, were calculated. The findings were then evaluated and presented in tables and figures to highlight patterns and variances across age

Ethical Consideration:

The data collection for this study was carried out after obtaining ethical approval from the relevant institutional review boards of multiple Tertiary Care Hospitals in Peshawar.

RESULTS

The purpose of the study was to investigate the common causes of dysphagia among different age groups on barium swallow in tertiary care hospitals Peshawar. The study analyzed 101 people experiencing dysphagia, classified by age, gender, nationality, swallowing trouble, weight loss, and related medical disorders.

Age distribution:

The majority of patients fall within the 21 to 40 years age representing 33.7% (34 patients) of the sample, the next common age group is 41 to 60 years accounting for 24.8% (25) of patients. Patients aged 61 to 80 years make up 22.8% (23 patients), while the 1 to 20 years age group represent 18.8% (19) patients of study population as shown in table 1.

TABLE: 1 AGE OF PATIENT

	Frequency	Percent
1-20	19	18.8
21-40	34	33.7
41-60	25	24.8
61-80	23	22.8
Total	101	100.0

Fig 1 Age distribution

Gender distribution:

The results show that 56.4% (57) patients were male and 43.6% (44) were females. This data

reveals a slightly higher prevalence of dysphagia in males compared to females with a male to female ratio of 1.2:1 as shown in table 2.

TABLE: 2 GENDER OF PATIENT

	Frequency	Percent
Male	57	56.4
Female	44	43.6
Total	101	100.0

Fig.2 Gender Distribution

Nationality

The results show a clear distribution of nationalities among the respondents, with a total of 101 participants. The majority, 64.4% (65 people) identified as Pakistani, while 35.6% (36

people) identified as Afghani as shown in table 3. This data shows a large predominance of Pakistani responses, indicating a noticeable skew in nationality representation.

Table: 3 Nationality

	Frequency	Percent
Pakistani	65	64.4
Afghani	36	35.6
Total	101	100.0

FIG.3 NATIONALITY

Difficulty in swallowing

Table 4 demonstrates that 57.4% (58) of patients experienced difficulties swallowing solids. In

comparison, just 7.9% of patients (8) struggled with liquids. Additionally, 34.7% (35) individuals experienced difficulties with both solids and liquids.

TABLE:4 DIFFICULTY IN SWALLOWING

	Frequency	Percent
Solid	58	57.4
Liquid	8	7.9
Both	35	34.7
Total	101	100.0

Fig.4 Difficulty in swallowing

Weight loss among dysphagia patients:
The examination of weight changes among the patients in Table.4.5 revealed that a major portion

had weight loss, with 56 patients (55.4%) and 45 patients (44.6%) reporting no weight changes.

Table 5 Weight loss

	Frequency	Percent
Yes, weight loss	56	55.4
No, weight changes	45	44.6
Total	101	100.0

FIG.5 WEIGHT LOSS

Distribution of medical conditions associated with dysphagia:

Table 6 shows the distribution of underlying causes of dysphagia in 101 patients.

Achalasia was the most common cause, involving 36 patients (35.6%), followed by esophageal

strictures, which were found in 28 individuals (27.7%). 12 patients (11.9%) had esophageal carcinoma, 11 patients (10.9%) had GERD, and 5 patients (5%) reported acid intake. These findings identify achalasia and strictures as the most prevalent causes of dysphagia in this population.

TABLE 6 MEDICAL CONDITION ASSOCIATED

	Frequency	Percent
GERD	11	10.9
Esophageal carcinoma	12	11.9
Systematic sclerosis	9	8.9
Achalasia	36	35.6
Strictures	28	27.7
Acid ingestion	5	5.0
Total	101	100.0

Fig.6. Medical conditions associated with dysphagia.

Age distribution of medical conditions associated with dysphagia across various age groups:

The table 7 documenting the age of patients in connection to various medical conditions associated with dysphagia shows distinct trends across different age groups among the 101 patients evaluated. The most prevalent condition in the 1-20 age group (19 patients) was achalasia, with 5 cases, followed by strictures (3 cases) and GERD. Achalasia was again the most prevalent in the 21-40 age range (34 patients), with strictures affecting 7 and a few cases of acid intake (2). Esophageal

carcinoma was the most common cause among individuals aged 41 to 60 (25 patients), followed by achalasia (7 instances) and strictures. Strictures were prevalent in the 61-80 age group (23 patients), affecting 13 patients, whereas systemic sclerosis was observed in 5 patients, and other disorders were less common. These findings indicate that achalasia is a prominent issue among younger patients (22 out of 43), while strictures (13 out of 23) and esophageal carcinoma become more significant in older age groups.

TABLE 7: MEDICAL CONDITIONS ACROSS VARIOUS AGE GROUP

Age of patient	Medical condition associated						Total
	GERD	Esophageal carcinoma	Systematic sclerosis	Achalasia	Strictures	Acid ingestion	
1-20	9	1	0	5	3	1	19
21-40	1	2	0	22	7	2	34
41-60	0	7	4	7	5	0	25
61-80	1	2	5	2	13		23
Total	11	12	9	36	28	5	101

8 Chi square test:

The Pearson Chi-Square test result ($\chi^2 = 70.894$, $df = 15$, $p < .001$) indicates a statistically significant association between the variables. However, the

validity of the test may be affected, as 66.7% of the cells have expected counts less than 5, violating the assumption for reliable chi-square results.

Table 8: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	70.894 ^a	15	.000
Likelihood Ratio	66.545	15	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.604	1	.032
N of Valid Cases	101		

a. 16 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .94.

DISCUSSION

Dysphagia, a syndrome marked by swallowing difficulties, affects millions globally and can profoundly influence quality of life. It originates from multiple factors, including brain illnesses, anatomical anomalies, and systemic diseases, frequently resulting in insufficient nutrition and aspiration-related health issues. Precise diagnosis of the underlying causes and severity of dysphagia is essential for efficient management and treatment. Prompt evaluation facilitates the identification of suitable therapies, hence enhancing patient outcomes. This study employed barium swallow to evaluate the prevalence and distribution of dysphagia in a sample of 101 individuals, allowing for an examination of the prevalent causes and demographic characteristics linked to this disease. The characteristics analyzed in our study were age, gender, nationality, weight loss, and difficulty in swallowing food, liquids, or both, along with the distribution of causes across different age groups. Patients were categorized into four age groups: 1 to 20 years, 21 to 40 years, 41 to 60 years, and 61 to 80 years. Our data indicated that dysphagia was most widespread in the 19 to 40 age group, including 33.7% of cases, followed by the 41 to 60 age group at 24.8%. Individuals aged 61 to 80 years represented 22.8%, and those in the 1-20 age range accounted for 18.8%. This distribution underscores the notable prevalence of dysphagia among different age demographics, especially in younger adults. In comparison Eslick

et al identified a greater prevalence in the 40-49 age group especially related to GERD, indicating the potential involvement of distinct risk factors. This highlights the necessity for specialized strategies in the diagnosis and management of dysphagia across various age groups (80). Another study conducted by Hamidon et al (2006) examined dysphagia after to acute ischemic stroke, involving 134 individuals. Their research found that age, especially in individuals aged 75 and older, in conjunction with diabetes, predicted the development of dysphagia following a stroke. Hamidon's findings underscore age-related concerns, particularly in older populations, but our work emphasizes the necessity of acknowledging dysphagia in younger persons as well. This alignment indicates that age is a crucial determinant; nevertheless, a wider spectrum of age demographics and underlying problems should be considered in both study and clinical practice (73). In our study, we evaluated the variable of gender and discovered that 56.4% (57 patients) of individuals with dysphagia were male, whereas 43.6% (44 patients) were female, suggesting a marginally greater frequency in males with a male-to-female ratio of 1.2:1. This finding indicates a gender disparity in the prevalence of dysphagia within our sample. The male preponderance aligns with prior research that indicate a higher occurrence of dysphagia in males compared to

women. For example, Iltaf et al (2014) did a study to examine the causes of esophageal dysphagia in 98 individuals. Their data indicated that 62.2% of patients were male and 37.8% were female. These findings correspond with the greater representation of men in our study and highlight the propensity of men to develop dysphagia more frequently than women (88). Conversely, Wilkins et al conducted a survey on the frequency of dysphagia among primary care patients, comprising 947 participants aged 18 and above. Their study revealed that dysphagia was largely reported by women (about 80.8%) and primarily affected older persons, notably those around 48 years of age. Our findings reveal a higher incidence in males; nevertheless, Wilkins et al proposed that females, especially older persons, may encounter elevated rates in primary care environments. The disparities in gender distribution

may arise from demographic variables within the study groups, highlighting the necessity for additional research to elucidate the underlying causes contributing to gender differences in dysphagia prevalence (74). In our study, 64.4% patients were identified as Pakistani, and 35.6% as Afghani, demonstrating a significant skew in nationality representation. In comparison, Iltaf et al (2014) stated that 52% of their patients were Pakistanis and 48% were Afghani, indicating a more balanced demographic. Upon investigating dysphagia, we discovered that 57.4% (58 patients) encountered issues with solid foods, but merely 7.9% (8 patients) faced challenges with liquids. Furthermore, 34.7% (35 patients) encountered challenges with both solid and liquid intake. Wilkins and colleagues conducted a survey on the frequency of dysphagia in primary care patients, encompassing 947 participants aged 18 and older, and reported comparable findings. Of the individuals reporting dysphagia, 49.0% encountered difficulties with solid foods exclusively, 6.3% with liquids exclusively, and 44.7% with both, highlighting the significance of swallowing difficulties. However, demographic variations imply that age and gender may affect the manifestation of dysphagia (74). The analysis of weight fluctuations in our patients found that a substantial number had weight loss, with 56

patients (55.4%) reporting this condition, while 45 patients (44.6%) reported no changes in weight. In comparison O. Ekberg et al conducted a study examining the social and psychological burden of dysphagia and its effect on quality of life. Their study encompassed 360 dysphagia patients with a mean age of 71.6 years. Half of the patients reported reduction in food intake, and 44% had experienced weight loss in the year preceding the trial. Additionally, 32% of patients reported having undergone professional therapy for their dysphagia, whereas merely 39% were optimistic about their solution of their swallowing difficulties. Significantly, 41% expressed emotions of panic or anxiety during meals (56). These data corroborate our study by emphasizing the incidence of weight loss in patients with dysphagia. Both results underscore the substantial influence of dysphagia on nutritional status and overall quality of life. The psychological factors identified by Ekberg et al emphasize the necessity of treating both the physical issues of dysphagia and the associated emotional and social repercussions, highlighting the requirement for comprehensive management solutions in clinical practice (56). Our analysis revealed that achalasia was the predominant cause of dysphagia, affecting 35.6% (36 patients), followed by esophageal strictures at 27.7%. Additional causes comprised esophageal cancer (11.9%) and gastro-esophageal reflux disease (10.9%). These findings highlight achalasia and strictures as the primary causes in our community, mirroring trends observed in the literature. Conversely, G D Eslick et al investigated the epidemiology and risk factors linked with dysphagia in a community context with 1,000 participants in Sydney, Australia. Research indicated that GERD markedly elevated the risk of dysphagia, especially in individuals aged 40 to 49 years. Our study highlights achalasia and strictures as the primary causes of dysphagia, whereas Eslick's findings emphasize GERD as significant risk factor, indicating that prevalence and underlying reasons may differ among population (72). Lindgren et al similarly evaluated swallowing symptoms in persons aged 50 to 79 years, noting that globus feeling and gastro-esophageal reflux (GER) were prevalent, affecting 35% of

participants. Our study finds achalasia and strictures as the primary causes of dysphagia, while Lindgren et al highlight gastro-esophageal reflux (GER) as a notable concern among older persons (69). Iltaf et al (2014) examined esophageal dysphagia at HMC Peshawar, observing a greater incidence of esophageal cancer and strictures among their 98 patients, primarily males aged 40 to 45. This comparison emphasizes the differences in etiology among various populations, highlighting the necessity for tailored strategies in the diagnosis and management of dysphagia. Additional research is necessary to investigate these variances for enhanced therapies (80). Our findings and the given literature reveal significant patterns and variations in the common causes of dysphagia among various age groups. Our findings demonstrate that GERD is the predominant condition in younger individuals of age group 1 to 20 years, while achalasia is most common in those aged 21-40 years, whereas esophageal cancer gains prominence in the 41-60 age range. Among those in the 61 to 80 age range, strictures were the predominant condition, impacting 13 patients, whereas systemic sclerosis was observed in 5 cases. This contrasts with Bhattacharyya's (2014) study, which revealed stroke and neurological diseases as predominant causes among adults, indicating that

achalasia may be under-represented in general populations relative to our specific cohort (85). The study by Lindgren et al investigated swallowing and esophageal complaints in individuals aged 50 to 79, revealing gastro-esophageal reflux (GER) and globus feeling as prominent concerns, indicating that functional disorders are common in older adults. Our findings highlight structural factors, such as strictures, as the predominant issue in individuals over 60 years of age. This mismatch may indicate variations in patient demographics, sample sizes, or preexisting health issues. Both studies recognize substantial swallowing difficulties in elderly populations; however, Lindgren et al emphasize functional concerns, while our findings indicate a necessity for more focus on structural abnormalities (77). Iltaf et al (2014) substantiate our findings that esophageal cancer is a notable cause of dysphagia in the 41-60 age demographic, highlighting the necessity for careful diagnosis and management of this illness in older patients. Our findings reveal specific trends, especially for strictures in individuals over 60, although the inconsistencies with existing literature indicate differing underlying causes of dysphagia that require more investigation across other populations (88)

CONCLUSION

Dysphagia is a concerning symptom that can lead to malnutrition and weight loss, necessitating prompt diagnosis. The barium swallow test effectively identifies both functional and anatomical issues in the esophagus, aiding in diagnosis and management. This study highlights that cardia achalasia is the most prevalent cause of dysphagia especially in younger individuals, followed by strictures in older patients. Dysphagia was found to be more common in males aged 21-40, many of whom experienced significant weight loss and trouble swallowing solids.

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